

Urinary IL-1 β and plasma IFN- γ levels reveal complementary immune mechanisms in endometriosis

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Abstract

Objectives: Endometriosis is a multifactorial inflammatory disorder characterized by the coexistence of localized inflammatory activation and systemic immune dysregulation. Single biomarkers are unlikely to capture this biological complexity, underscoring the need for integrated immune profiling across different biological compartments. This pilot study evaluated interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and interferon- γ (IFN- γ) in paired plasma and urine samples from women with clinically confirmed endometriosis and healthy controls to explore compartment-specific cytokine patterns.

Methods: IL-1 β and IFN- γ were quantified in plasma and urine samples from patients with endometriosis and healthy control women using the automated microfluidic ELISA system (Ella, ProteinSimple/Bio-Techne, USA). Marker detectability and expression patterns were evaluated individually. The expression levels were compared using the Mann–Whitney *U* test.

Results: IL-1 β was undetectable in plasma samples in both groups but was detected in urine samples from patients with endometriosis but not in controls ($p = 0.0303$). In contrast, IFN- γ was detectable in plasma but not in urine. Plasma IFN- γ levels were lower in patients compared with controls; however, this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.99$) and should be interpreted only as a descriptive trend.

Conclusion: The findings of this study suggest compartment-specific immune differences in endometriosis, with urinary IL-1 β reflecting localized inflammatory activity and plasma IFN- γ showing a trend toward reduced systemic T helper 1 (Th1)-associated immunity. Larger studies are required to validate these preliminary observations. This complementary biomarker profile underscores the importance of integrated interpretation across biological systems and supports a minimally invasive immune signature for improved characterization of endometriosis.

Keywords

Biomarkers, endometriosis, noninvasive

Introduction

Endometriosis is a chronic, estrogen-dependent inflammatory disease that affects an estimated 10–15% of women of reproductive age worldwide and represents a major cause of pelvic pain, dysmenorrhea, and infertility (Garmendia et al. 2025). Despite its significant impact on quality of life, diagnosis remains challenging and is often delayed for several years, largely due to the absence of reliable noninvasive biomarkers (Agic et al. 2006; Garmendia et al. 2025). This diagnostic gap reflects the biological complexity of the disease, which arises from the interplay between hormonal regulation and immune dysfunction rather than a single dominant pathogenic pathway.

One of the prevailing theories for the occurrence of endometriosis is the underlying process of immune dysregulation, which contributes both to lesion establishment and persistence. Alterations have been described across multiple components of the immune system, including enhanced macrophage activation, impaired natural killer (NK) cell cytotoxicity, imbalances in T helper cell subsets, and aberrant B-cell responses (Abramiuk et al. 2022; Vallvé-Juanico et al. 2022). Together, these changes promote an inflammatory microenvironment that favors ectopic tissue survival while limiting effective immune clearance. Within this context, cytokines play a pivotal role as mediators of immune communication, tissue remodeling, angiogenesis, and pain signaling (Bergqvist et al. 2001; Uçeyler et al. 2007; Turner et al. 2014).

Numerous studies have reported elevated concentrations of pro-inflammatory cytokines—including interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α)—in endometriotic lesions and peritoneal fluid, with less consistent findings in peripheral blood (Bergqvist et al. 2001; Krygere et al. 2024). However, translation into clinically useful biomarkers has been limited due to variability across menstrual cycle phase, lesion localization, disease stage, and biological compartment. Cytokine measurements are also influenced by systemic inflammatory conditions and lack disease specificity, limiting the utility of single-marker approaches (Agic et al. 2006). As a result, single cytokine measurements often fail to reflect the underlying complexity of the disease.

Most immunological studies in endometriosis focus on serum and peritoneal fluid, where numerous cytokines, such as IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and MCP-1, are elevated compared with controls and correlate with disease activity or severity (Wu and Ho 2003). There are very few direct studies measuring classical cytokines, such as IL-6, IL-8, MCP-1, and TNF- α , in urine from patients with endometriosis as diagnostic biomarkers (Liu et al. 2015). Some studies have measured solitary urinary proteins related to inflammation, such as cytokeratin-19 fragment (CYFRA 21-1) (Saputra et al. 2025), urinary vitamin D-binding protein (Cho et al. 2012), urocortin, and other non-cytokine markers (Toma et al. 2025). Urine has long been shown to be a reliable source of diagnostic material; however, classical cytokines are often present at very low concentrations or below detection limits. Evidence about the

levels of classical cytokines in urine is so far limited and inconclusive.

Among the immune mediators of endometriosis, IL-1 β and IFN- γ represent distinct and complementary aspects of immune function. IL-1 β is a key driver of innate inflammatory responses and is produced primarily by activated macrophages. It has been repeatedly shown to be upregulated in endometriosis tissue and peritoneal fluid, where it promotes leukocyte recruitment, angiogenesis, and local inflammation (Sikora et al. 2016). In contrast, IFN- γ is a hallmark cytokine of T helper 1 (Th1)-mediated immunity and plays a critical role in cellular immune surveillance and macrophage activation (Castro et al. 2018).

In this study, IL-1 β and IFN- γ levels were measured in paired urine and plasma samples obtained from individuals with endometriosis and from controls without the disease. By evaluating those two protein markers, this study aims to identify a complementary immune signature that reflects both local and systemic aspects of endometriosis. This approach explores the potential of cytokine patterns as a minimally invasive strategy for improving disease identification.

Materials and methods

Study participants

A total of 16 women were included in this study: 10 patients with endometriosis (mean age 34 years) and six healthy control women of the same ethnicity (mean age 22 years). All participants provided written informed consent for participation in the study, and the study protocol was approved by the Ethical Committee of the Scientific Council of the Medical University—Sofia, Bulgaria (Approval No. 2826/24.06.2025, Protocol No.13/05.06.2025). All women were diagnosed with confirmed, non-surgically treated endometriosis and were selected at the University Hospital “Lozenets” or Medical Complex “D-r Shterev” (Table 1).

Sample collection and storage

Peripheral venous blood was collected in EDTA tubes and centrifuged at 2,000 \times g for 10 mins to separate the plasma. Plasma samples were aliquoted and stored at -80°C until analysis. Morning midstream urine samples were collected, aliquoted, and similarly stored at -80°C .

Cytokine quantification using the Ella[®] system

Plasma and urine concentrations of IL-1 β and IFN- γ (pg/mL) were measured using the Ella automated immunoassay system (ProteinSimple/Bio-Techne, MN, USA). The Ella system is a fully automated, microfluidic-based platform that performs multiplexed sandwich ELISA assays in nanoliter-scale volumes. The system reports mean RFU (relative fluorescence units), RFU %CV, mean concentration, and concentration %CV, enabling direct quantification of cytokine concentrations with built-in quality control. Each sample was assayed at a 1:2 dilution for both plasma and urine.

Table 1. Clinical and demographic characteristics of the study groups.

Number	Sample code	Age	Diagnosis
Patients			
1	P1-PR	37	endometriosis
2	P2-PR	28	endometriosis
3	P3-PR	27	endometriosis
4	P4-PR	32	endometriosis
5	P9-PR	43	endometriosis
6	PR-P10	37	endometriosis
7	PR-P15	34	endometriosis
8	PR-P16	34	endometriosis
9	PR-P17	36	endometriosis
10	PR-P20	32	endometriosis
Controls			
1	PR-C2	27	control group
2	PR-C10	19	control group
3	PR-C11	21	control group
4	PR-C12	20	control group
5	PR-C13	21	control group
6	PR-C17	22	control group

Data presentation and statistical analysis

IL-1 β and IFN- γ levels were quantified in plasma and urine samples from 10 women with endometriosis and six healthy controls and are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Due to the limited sample size and non-normal distribution of the data, between-group comparisons of protein concentrations (pg/mL) were performed using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney *U* test. Statistical analyses were conducted using GraphPad Prism version 10.6.1 (GraphPad Software, Boston, MA, USA). A *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results below the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) were replaced with LLOQ/2. Results with a coefficient of variation > 25% were excluded.

Results

IL-1 β and IFN- γ in plasma and urine

IL-1 β was undetectable in plasma samples from both patients and controls.

Urinary IL-1 β levels differed between groups (*p* = 0.0303), with higher levels observed in women with endometriosis (mean = 4.99 pg/mL) compared with controls (mean = 0.75 pg/mL). The distribution of urinary IL-1 β concentrations measured using the Ella[®] system is shown in Fig. 1.

IFN- γ was not detectable in urine samples from either group.

In plasma, IFN- γ was detectable in both groups. Mean levels were lower in patients with endometriosis compared with controls (0.70 pg/mL vs 1.54 pg/mL). However, this difference was not statistically significant (*p* > 0.99) and is therefore reported only as a descriptive observation.

The plasma IFN- γ concentrations are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1. The distribution of urinary IL-1 β concentrations measured by the automated ELISA system Ella[®] (ProteinSimple/Bio-Techne, USA) in pg/mL in patients with endometriosis and control individuals. * indicates statistical significance between the analyzed groups (*p* = 0.0303).

Figure 2. The distribution of plasma IFN- γ concentrations measured by the automated ELISA system Ella[®] (Bio-Techne, Boston, USA) in pg/mL in patients with endometriosis and control individuals. "ns" indicates a lack of statistical significance between the analyzed groups (*p* > 0.99).

Discussion

In this study, the protein expression of IL-1 β and IFN- γ was investigated in paired plasma and urine samples from women with endometriosis and healthy controls. The findings suggest differential cytokine detectability depending on the studied biological fluid, as well as on disease status.

IL-1 β appeared undetectable in plasma samples from both groups, supporting the concept that endometriosis is primarily characterized by localized rather than overt systemic inflammation (Giudice and Kao 2004; Bulun et al. 2009). In contrast, IL-1 β was vaguely detectable in urine samples from women with endometriosis, whereas it remained largely undetectable in controls. Despite the small

number of samples, this observation demonstrated a clear trend toward higher urinary IL-1 β levels in patients with endometriosis. This is consistent with the participation of IL-1 β in inflammasome activation, angiogenesis, and inflammatory amplification within the pelvic microenvironment (Lebovic et al. 2001; Dinarello et al. 2011). IL-1 β has been consistently reported as elevated in the peritoneal fluid of women with endometriosis, where it contributes to immune cell recruitment (Lebovic et al. 2001; Sikora et al. 2018). The detection of IL-1 β in urine may be caused by localized pelvic inflammation, potentially offering a non-invasive way to monitor the inflammatory activity associated with the disease.

In contrast, IFN- γ was undetectable in urine in both groups, suggesting limited urinary excretion or absent local production in this compartment. Plasma IFN- γ levels were lower in patients with endometriosis compared with controls; however, this difference was not statistically significant and should be interpreted cautiously as a possible rather than a confirmed biological effect. IFN- γ is predominantly produced by Th1 CD4+ T cells, cytotoxic CD8+ T cells, and natural killer (NK) cells and directs macrophage activation and enhanced antigen presentation, which are essential for the effective clearance of aberrant cells (Castro et al. 2018; Alspach et al. 2019). Relatively lower systemic IFN- γ levels in patients, if confirmed, could reflect a shift away from Th1 immunity, which is mainly implicated in endometriosis pathogenesis, particularly through NK cell dysfunction and reduced cytotoxicity against ectopic endometrial tissue (Reis et al. 2022; Chen et al. 2023).

IFN- γ cannot currently be considered a candidate biomarker in this dataset, and the trend toward lower plasma IFN- γ in patients warrants further investigation, particularly using larger cohorts or in combination with functional assays to assess Th1 and NK cell activity. This may be of interest for future hypothesis-driven studies examining systemic Th1 activity in endometriosis.

Limitations of the study

Importantly, several limitations must be acknowledged. The study comprises a relatively small cohort (10 patients and six controls), which limits the statistical power and increases the likelihood of type II error. The observed statistical significance for urinary IL-1 β should be interpreted with caution. Even if the observed trend is biologically consistent with the current understanding of localized inflammatory activation in endometriosis, it should be validated in a larger number of samples.

Several clinically relevant variables that may influence cytokine levels were not controlled in this study, including menstrual cycle phase, hormonal therapy status, BMI, disease stage, and lesion localization. These factors are known to significantly affect immune signaling and cytokine expression in endometriosis. Future studies should incorporate stratification for these variables.

Strengths of the study

Despite these limitations, the present study has several notable strengths. The parallel assessment of cytokines in two biological compartments (plasma and urine) provides a compartment-specific perspective that is rarely explored in endometriosis research. Most previous studies have focused on serum or peritoneal fluid; therefore, the inclusion of urine expands the perspectives toward the evaluation of a noninvasive sampling matrix. The findings are biologically coherent with the current understanding of endometriosis as a localized inflammatory disorder. The selective detection of IL-1 β in urine from patients aligns with established evidence of IL-1-mediated pelvic inflammation and inflammasome activation (Lebovic et al. 2001; Dinarello et al. 2011).

Conclusion

In summary, this pilot study suggests a distinct compartment-specific immune pattern in endometriosis, characterized by detectable urinary IL-1 β and a nonsignificant reduction in plasma IFN- γ . This combination reflects the dual nature of the disease, involving localized pelvic inflammation alongside altered systemic Th1-mediated immune responses. Larger, controlled studies are required to validate these observations before any possible clinical utility consideration and application.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

All participants provided written informed consent for participation in the study, and the study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Sofia (Approval No. 2826/24.06.2025, Protocol No.13/05.06.2025)

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed in the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalized human or animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

No AI tools were used in the preparation of this manuscript.

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Author contributions

E.Dimova-Mihaylova has collected part of the samples at “Lozenetz” hospital, has performed the experiments, has made the statistical analysis; I.Dimova has participated in the statistical analysis of the data and has suggested some interpretations; P.Andreeva has collected the blood/urine samples at the Medical complex “D-r Shterev” and has selected the patients; D.Nikolova has participated in the experiments and analysis, suggested improvements, interpretations and critically revised the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Abramiuk M, Grywalska E, Malkowska P, Sierawska O, Hrynkiewicz R, Niedzwiedzka-Rystwej P (2022) The role of the immune system in the development of endometriosis. *Cells* 11(13): 2028. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells11132028>
- Agic A, Xu H, Finas D, Banz C, Diedrich K, Hornung D (2006) Is endometriosis associated with systemic subclinical inflammation? *Gynecologic and Obstetric Investigation* 62(3): 139–147. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000093121>
- Alsapach E, Lussier DM, Schreiber RD (2019) Interferon γ and its important roles in promoting and inhibiting spontaneous and therapeutic cancer immunity. *Cold Spring Harbor Perspectives Biology* 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.1101/cshperspect.a028480>
- Bergqvist A, Bruse C, Carlberg M, Carlström K (2001) Interleukin 1beta, interleukin-6, and tumor necrosis factor-alpha in endometriotic tissue and in endometrium. *Fertility and Sterility* 75(3): 489–495. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0015-0282\(00\)01752-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0015-0282(00)01752-0)
- Bulun SE (2009) Endometriosis. *The New England Journal of Medicine* 360(3): 268–279. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMra0804690>
- Castro F, Cardoso AP, Gonçalves RM, Serre K, Oliveira MJ (2018) Interferon-gamma at the crossroads of tumor immune surveillance or evasion. *Frontiers in Immunology* 9: 2028. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2018.00847>
- Chen S, Liu Y, Zhong Z, Wei C, Liu Y, Zhu X (2023) Peritoneal immune microenvironment of endometriosis: Role and therapeutic perspectives. *Frontiers in Immunology* 14: 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2023.1134663>
- Cho S, Choi YS, Yim SY, Yang HI, Jeon YE, Lee KE, Lee BS (2012) Urinary vitamin D-binding protein is elevated in patients with endometriosis. *Human Reproduction* 27(2): 515–522. <https://doi.org/10.1093/humrep/der345>
- Dinarello CA (2011) Interleukin-1 in the pathogenesis and treatment of inflammatory diseases. *Blood* 117(14): 3720–3732. <https://doi.org/10.1182/blood-2010-07-273417>
- Garmendia JV, De Sanctis CV, Hajduch M, De Sanctis JB (2025) Endometriosis: An immunologist's perspective. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 26(11): 5193. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26115193>
- Giudice LC, Kao LC (2004) Endometriosis. *The Lancet* 364(9447): 1789–1799. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(04\)17403-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(04)17403-5)
- Krygere L, Jukna P, Jariene K, Drejeriene E (2024) Diagnostic potential of cytokine biomarkers in endometriosis: Challenges and insights. *Biomedicines* 12(12): 2867. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines12122867>
- Lebovic DI, Mueller MD, Taylor RN (2001) Immunobiology of endometriosis. *Fertility and Sterility* 75(1): 1–10. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0015-0282\(00\)01630-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0015-0282(00)01630-7)
- Liu E, Nisenblat V, Farquhar C, Fraser I, Bossuyt PM, Johnson N, Hull ML (2015) Urinary biomarkers for the non-invasive diagnosis of endometriosis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic reviews* 2015(12). <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd012019>
- Reis JL, Rosa NN, Ângelo-Dias M, Martins C, Borrego LM, Lima J (2022) Natural killer cell receptors and endometriosis: A systematic review. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 24(1): 331. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24010331>
- Saputra NPK, Samsulhadi S, Hendarto H, Sa'adi A, Pudjirahardjo WJ, Arsana IW, Yanuari R, Dwiningasih SR (2025) Strengthening of CYFRA 21–1 using urine creatinine correction as potential endometriosis biomarker. *F1000Research* 13: 46. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.135167.2>
- Sikora J, Mielczarek-Palacz A, Kondera-Anasz Z (2016) Association of the precursor of interleukin-1 β and peritoneal inflammation-role in pathogenesis of endometriosis. *Journal of Clinical Laboratory Analysis* 30(6): 831–837. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jcla.21944>
- Sikora J, Smycz-Kubańska M, Mielczarek-Palacz A, Bednarek I, Kondera-Anasz Z (2018) The involvement of multifunctional TGF- β and related cytokines in pathogenesis of endometriosis. *Immunology Letters* 201: 31–37. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imlet.2018.10.011>
- Toma B, Caruntu ID, Simionescu N, Onofriescu M, Socolov D, Ilea C, Socolov R (2025) Urinary urocortin as a potential non-invasive biomarker in endometriosis: Exploratory study with histone H4. *Medicina* 61(9): 1671. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina61091671>
- Turner MD, Nedjai B, Hurst T, Pennington DJ (2014) Cytokines and chemokines: At the crossroads of cell signalling and inflammatory disease. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA) – Molecular Cell Research* 1843(11): 2563–2582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamcr.2014.05.014>
- Uçeyler N, Rogausch JP, Toyka KV, Sommer C (2007) Differential expression of cytokines in painful and painless neuropathies. *Neurology* 69(1): 42–49. <https://doi.org/10.1212/01.wnl.0000265062.92340.a5>
- Vallvé-Juanico J, George AE, Sen S, Thomas R, Shin MG, Kushnoor D, Giudice LC (2022) Deep immunophenotyping reveals endometriosis is marked by dysregulation of the mononuclear phagocytic system in endometrium and peripheral blood. *BMC Med* 20(1): 158. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-022-02359-4>
- Wu MY, Ho HN (2003) The role of cytokines in endometriosis. *American Journal of Reproductive Immunology* 49(5): 285–296. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1600-0897.2003.01207.x>